

Review

Comparing Voltage Waveforms Simulation vs. Microcontroller-Based Single-Phase

Kamal Mohamed Saied ^{1*}, Rafia Khalleefah Hamad Mohammed², Ahmed nassar³, Salah H.E.Salah⁴, Waled yahya⁵

¹Electrical Engineering Department, Bright Star University, Brega, Libya

²Department of Technical Engineering, Bright Star University, Brega, Libya

³Mechanical Engineering Department, Higher Institute for Science and Technology, Zuwaytinah, Libya

⁴High institute of science and Technology, Emsaad, Libya

⁵Department of Management Science and Engineering, Shanghai University, Shanghai, China

Abstract: Significant advancements in electromechanical systems have led to the widespread adoption of induction motors in various electronic devices due to their simplicity, effective torque control, direct connection to AC sources, low maintenance costs, robustness, and durability. This study aims to compare the motor waveform voltages between simulation and experimental results using Matlab/Simulink software and hardware. An AT89C52 microcontroller-based variable frequency power inverter is used to control the speed of a single-phase induction motor. In order to maintain the necessary PWM frequency with the fewest possible harmonics at the inverter output, the microcontroller produces variable frequency pulse width modulation (PWM) signals that regulate the applied voltage on the gate drive. Isolated gate bipolar transistors (IGBTs) are used to create a fully controlled bridge voltage source that uses the PWM technique to provide the motor with AC voltage. Matlab/Simulink is used to simulate the single-phase variable frequency inverter, and experimental data revealed a strong correlation between the simulation and hardware outcomes for the microcontroller-based inverter.

Keywords: Induction Motor; Microcontroller, Single phase power Inverter

*Corresponding Author: Kamal Mohamed Saied, E-mail: Kamal.Azged@bsu.edu.ly

Accepted: 28 December, 2024; **Published:** 29 December, 2024

How to cite this article: Kamal Mohamed Saied , Rafia Khalleefah Hamad Mohammed, Ahmed nassar, Salah H.E.Salah, Waled yahya (2024). Comparing Voltage Waveforms Simulation vs. Microcontroller-Based Single-Phase. *North American Academic Research*, 7(12), 413-419 . doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14606411>

Conflicts of Interest: There are no conflicts to declare.

Publisher's Note: NAAR stays neutral about jurisdictional claims in published maps/image and institutional affiliations.

Copyright: ©2024 by the authors. Author(s) are fully responsible for the text, figure, data in this manuscript submitted for possible open access publication under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

Introduction

The main advantages of AC induction motors are their simple and robust design, low cost, low maintenance, and direct connection to an AC power source. Induction motors, also known as asynchronous motors, are a type of alternating current motor where power is supplied to the rotor by electromagnetic induction. Over a considerable period of time, induction motors have been used in greater numbers across a wide variety of industrial and commercial applications because they provide numerous benefits and are a dependable device to convert electrical energy into mechanical motion [1]. Because single phase power supplies are more readily available, single phase

induction motors (SPIMs) are actually frequently used in domestic settings, such as dishwashers, clothes dryers, fans, and pumps.

Other applications for this system include electric vehicles, variable speed equipment, and AC variable frequency power sources used in laboratories where a variety of experiments necessitate the use of various AC sources with respect to frequency and voltage amplitude. As a result, it can be very helpful in the lab for testing equipment, products, and appliances. In an automated production line, it could also be useful for verifying that the device under test (DUT) is operating within a given voltage and frequency range. An induction motor, like most motors, consists of a rotor that rotates inside a stator, which is a fixed outer part, and a carefully designed air gap between the two. The rotors of almost all electrical motors are rotated by magnetic fields.

An induction motor, also known as a rotating transformer because the stator (stationary part) is essentially the primary side of the transformer and the rotor is the secondary side, uses rotating magnetic fields to transform the voltage; the current in the primary side creates an electromagnetic field that interacts with the electromagnetic field of the secondary side to produce a resultant torque, thereby transforming the electrical energy into mechanical energy. Induction motors are widely used, especially poly phase induction motors, which are commonly used in industrial settings.

Research Methodology

AT89C51 MicroController to drive the bridge of inverter, which is usually done by specific IC's. In this case, will adjust timing of switching in inverter circuit to make inverted wave closer to sin waves which would results in lower harmonics and consequently low heating losses. The microcontroller generates a variable frequency pulse width modulation (PWM) signal that regulates the voltage applied to the gate drive, ensuring that the power inverter's output has minimal harmonic distortion. In a single-phase variable frequency inverter, a full-bridge diode rectifier is powered by a 230 Vac supply. The rectifier converts the AC voltage to a DC voltage of 12V.

A smoothing capacitor is used to filter out the ripples from the DC voltage. The smoothed DC voltage is then supplied to a single-bridge IGBT inverter, which transforms the 12V DC into a variable-frequency 230V AC output to control the motor. Matlab/Simulink SimPower Systems software will use as a tool to simulate the circuit which consists of full bridge rectifier, PWM generator, universal bridge, asynchronous machine and a Scope that displays the signals generated throughout the simulation.. Fig. 1 shows the complete system single phase induction motor.

Fig.1: Block diagram for single phase induction motor simulation circuit

The variable frequency pulse width modulation (PWM) signal controls the voltage applied to the gate drive, generating the required PWM frequency with minimal harmonic distortion at the output of the power inverter. The single-phase variable frequency inverter is composed of a full-bridge diode rectifier, which is powered by a 230V AC

supply. The rectifier bridge converts the AC supply voltage to a DC voltage of 12V. This DC voltage is then smoothed by a capacitor to reduce ripple. The resulting stable DC voltage is supplied to a single-bridge IGBT inverter, which converts the 12V DC into a variable frequency 230V AC output to drive the motor under control.

The following are the main characteristics of VF (Voltage-Frequency) control: An induction motor's base speed is directly correlated with both the motor's pole count and supply frequency. The ratio of the applied voltage to the supply frequency directly affects the torque produced by the induction motor. The torque can be maintained constant over the whole speed range by adjusting the voltage and frequency while keeping their ratio constant. This is VF control's main objective. To vary the supply frequency in a single-phase system, the process involves converting AC to DC and then converting DC back to AC. A rectifier circuit is used to convert AC to DC, while an inverter circuit is used to convert DC to AC.

An embedded controller is employed to generate the triggering pulses required by the inverter. The inverter then controls the motor speed, ensuring that the V/F ratio remains constant. In this project, a keypad is interfaced with the microcontroller, with different keys assigned to specific speeds. When a particular key is pressed, the motor will operate at the corresponding speed, and the speed will be displayed on an LCD. For converting AC into DC using ready made regulator block which is having current rating of 6 Amps and that output is in the form of pulsated DC. To convert that pulsated DC into constant DC using filter capacitor of rating 470 uf/450 V. That constant DC is converted into variable AC by using inverter circuit. Use bridge inverter with four IGBT'S for converting DC into AC.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The circuit, which consists of a full bridge rectifier, PWM generator, universal bridge, asynchronous machine, and a scope to display the signals produced during the simulation, has been simulated using Matlab/Simulink SimPower Systems software and Voltage Waveform Analysis for simulation .

Fig. 2: voltage waveforms for different values of frequency

For m=1, f=45 Hz. (b) For m=0.9, f=45 Hz.

(c) For $m=0.8$, $f=40$ Hz. (d) For $m=0.7$, $f=35$ Hz.

Fig. 2 (a to d) depicts the obtained voltage waveforms across the load at different values of frequency. Fig. 2 (a) shows that the voltage waveform 238V was obtained across the load at 50Hz, 1 m, 3000 rpm and 100% duty cycle. Fig. 2 (b) represents that the voltage waveform was found 235V across the load at 45Hz, 0.9 m, 2700 rpm and duty cycle 90%. Fig. 2 (c) represents that the voltage waveform was found 233V across the load at 40Hz, 0.8 m , 2400 rpm, and 80% duty cycle. Fig. 2 (d) demonstrates the voltage waveform was gained 230V across the load 35Hz, $m=0.7$, 2100 rpm and 70% duty cycle. Two inputs are sent to the PWM module: "duty cycle" and "frequency." The duty cycle can range from 70% to 100%, and the frequency can be adjusted between 20 Hz and 2 kHz. The frequency is converted from Hz to counts using the following formula in order to use the output compare function as a PWM generator.

$$FREQCENT = \frac{FREQHz}{0,5\mu s} \tag{1}$$

Where:

$0,5 \mu s$ is the one cycle period of microcontroller.

Speeds of motor results of the Speed signals output from the simulation

Fig. 3: Rate of speed at different ratio

Fig. 3 shows the Rate of speed of induction motor at different ratio from the obtained from the simulation. Here, four different ratio is marked at four distinct color such as 100% - red, 90%-blue, 80%-green and 70%- black. From the Fig. it is clarified that the speed control of motor at different ratio increased proportionally with the raising of time. Thus, All of them progressed almost at the same rate up to the half period (1.5s) with regard to total counting time. At 1.5 s, all of them they achieved around 2000 rpm speed. After wards, each of them advanced slightly different way. Indeed, after achieving 2000 rpm the speed of induction motor at 70% shifted to stable condition until ending time, while among the three others, rate of speed at 100% and 90% ratio moved forward at the same pace and gained 3000, 2700 rpm, respectively, and the other one reached the consolidated state obtaining 2500 rpm. And as you see in the Fig. the speed be on the steady state after that until 10s but actually it can be same until 1 hour.

Experimental Results

The hardware implementation involved using an AT89C51 microcontroller to drive the inverter bridge via IC drivers, adjusting switching times to produce a waveform closer to a sine wave. The experimental setup included separate DC supplies for the microcontroller and IC chips, with measurements taken across the load to observe the voltage waveform. An induction motor served as the load, allowing observation of load characteristics and the Figure 4

showed hardware circuit.

Fig. 4: Hardware circuit

First off, the 89C51 microcontroller requires an operating voltage of 5 V. Therefore, the system needs a 5 V A DC power supply. Using a step-down transformer, the 230V AC must first be reduced to 18V. The IGBT driver circuit, which regulates device switching, needs 12V as its operating voltage in addition to a higher current-driving capacity. Consequently, in order to generate this 12V, an additional power source is required. Bridge rectifiers are used in both power supplies to rectify the step-down AC voltage, and 1N4007 diodes are employed in this process. A "C" filter is subsequently used to smooth out the rectified AC voltage. A voltage regulator then receives the filtered DC voltage and produces a steady, controlled output voltage. A 7805 voltage regulator provides the 5V needed for the microcontroller, and a 7812 voltage regulator provides the 12V needed for the IGBT driver circuit.

Following regulation, filtering, and rectification, a 100 μ F electrolytic capacitor is used to further filter the voltage in order to lessen ripples. The 89C51 microcontroller has pull-up resistors at Port 0 and an 11.0592 MHz crystal oscillator connected to the 18th and 19th pins of the microcontroller, as well as a couple of capacitors to ensure proper operation. The operating voltage is provided by the regulated 5V output from the first power supply, which is supplied to the 40th pin of the microcontroller. The second power supply supplies 12V for the other circuitry. The LCD is interfaced with the microcontroller by connecting its data pins to Port 0 and its control pins to Port 2. Additionally, the keypad switches are connected to Port 3 of the microcontroller.

In this project, five opto couplers, each opto coupler has six pins in which 1st pin and 4th pin is connected to the supply and ground respectively is used. 3rd and 6th pins have no connection. Here we are using two IGBT Driver circuit; it is a 14th pin IC, the 1st opto coupler 5th pin goes to 10th pin of 1st IGBT IC and 2nd pin goes to p1.0 pin of microcontroller. The 2nd opto coupler 5th pin goes to 12th pin of 1st IGBT IC and 2nd pin goes to p1.1 of microcontroller. The 3rd opto coupler 5th pin goes to 11th pin of both IGBT IC and 2nd pin goes to p1.4 of microcontroller. The 4th opto coupler 5th pin goes to 10th pin of 2nd IGBT IC and 2nd pin goes to p1.2 of microcontroller. The 5th opto coupler 5th pin goes to 12th pin of 2nd IGBT IC and 2nd pin goes to p1.3 of microcontroller. The microcontroller gets the input through 2nd pin of Optocoupler. The microcontroller senses the no. of units being consumed and it will display on LCD. With every press of switch, speed of motor increases.

Voltage Waveform Results for Experimental

The PWM AC Voltage Controller was tested after the hardware schematic was connected to the power. A variable transformer was used to supply the power circuit with a sinusoidal voltage. All of the IC chips and the micro controller were powered by different DC sources. To view the load voltage waveform, the measurement device was connected across the load. By using an induction motor as the circuit's load, the load characteristics of the circuit could also be seen. A microcontroller has produced a variable frequency AC voltage at the single phase system's output voltage supplying an induction motor, as illustrated in Fig. 5 respectively.

Fig. 5: voltage waveforms for different values of frequency

(a) For $m=1$, $f=45$ Hz. (b) For $m=0.9$, $f=45$ Hz.

(c) For $m=0.8$, $f=40$ Hz. (d) For $m=0.7$, $f=35$ Hz.

Fig. 5 (a to d) illustrates the obtained voltage waveforms across the load at different values of frequency. Fig. 5(a) shows that the voltage waveform was found 238V across the load at 50Hz, 1 modulation index, 2979 rpm and 100% duty cycle. Fig. 5(b) indicates the voltage waveform was obtained 100% V across the load at 45Hz, 0.9 m, 2747 rpm and 90% duty cycle. Fig. 5(c) represents that the voltage waveform was achieved obtained 233V across the load at 40Hz, 0.8 m, 2501 rpm, and 80% duty cycle. Fig. 5(d) demonstrates that the voltage waveform was obtained across the load at 35Hz, 0.7 m, 2178 rpm and 70% duty cycle. Where the Modulation Index (m) = 1 at ratio 100% speed of motor.

Conclusion

This study successfully developed a variable frequency AC voltage generator for controlling the speed of a single-phase induction motor using a microcontroller. A comparison of waveform voltages between the simulation and experimental results, using Matlab/Simulink software and hardware, showed a strong correlation. The AT89C52 microcontroller-based single-phase variable frequency power inverter was found to be effective, with consistent results observed between the simulation and hardware implementations.

Author Contributions: At first page.

Approval: All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Funding: This research received no external funding.

Institutional Review Board Statement: Not applicable.

Informed Consent Statement: Not applicable.

Data Availability Statement: Not applicable

Acknowledgments: Not Mentioned.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

References

- [1]. Ali, K. and Abozaed, M. , 2010. Microcontroller Based Variable Frequency Power Inverter. Processing of the IMECS. ISBN: 978-988-18210-4-1. Vol II.
- [2]. Ali, K. , 2013. Precision Control of Single-Phase PWM Inverter Using M68HC11E Microcontroller. World Academy of Science, Engineering and Technology. Vol:7 2013-04-27.
- [3]. Yao, J. , 2000, Single Phase Induction Motor Adjustable Speed Control Using DSP and Microcontroller, Course Project for ECE734 Fall Semester at UW-Madison.
- [4]. Parekh, R. , 2003, AC Induction Motor Fundamentals, Microchip Technology Inc.
- [5]. Krishnan, R , 2007, Electric Motor Drives--Modeling, Analysis, and Control. New Delhi Prentice/Hall of India, pp. 317-345.
- [6]. L. Rimifriiu, M. Lucanu, C, Aghion, O. Ursaru, 2003. Control With Microcontroller For PWM Single-Phase Inverter IEEE, "Gh. Asachi" Technical University of Iasi, Faculty of Electronics and Telecommunications, Bd. Carol I, no. 11, Iasi, 700537 Romania.
- [7]. Vodovozov, V. and Vinnikov, D. , 2008 , Electronic System of Motor Drive, Tallinn University of Technology, Department of Electrical Drives and Power Electronics.

